

PILL STATS

Study Designs in Medical Research

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Approximately 85% of health research is believed to be wasted due to failure to publish, unclear and wrong reporting, poor study design and conduct, or does not consider what is already known in the topic area.¹ As a (bio)statistician and a researcher who frequently collaborates with medical doctors, I too have experienced that a rigorous study design is one of the vital factors in conducting accurate medical research. In the research process, after determining the research question, the choice of appropriate study design is necessary to find a valid and reliable answer, understand the conclusions drawn from the research and create new knowledge.²

Study designs have crucial roles in terms of quantitative and qualitative aspects: Building precise relations, recruiting the sufficient number of subjects, reducing selection bias of subjects and their measurement bias in data collection, purifying confounding effects and applying proper statistical methods to increase validity and reliability, enabling to replication, reproducibility and generalization of findings to large populations, considering of ethical issues to decrease potential harms, and optimal utilizing from resources such as budget, equipment and time.^{2,3}

Generally, in medical research, study designs are categorized into three parts mainly as observational, interventional, and systematic review/meta-analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Study design types on medical research

Observational studies involve observing and analyzing individuals or populations without intervening or assigning treatments. Observational study designs include cohort studies (following a group over a period), case-control studies (comparing individuals with a certain condition to those without), and cross-sectional studies (collecting data at a specific point in time). These studies can be prospective (collecting data moving forward) or retrospective (analyzing existing data).^{3,4}

Interventional studies observe a specified intervention's effect on animals or human (clinical trials). Clinical trials can be controlled or uncontrolled. In controlled trials, the experimental procedure, treatment or drug, is compared with a different treatment or drug. The controlled group can be a reference, standard control, or placebo. The interventional and controlled groups can be treated simultaneously (concurrently) or non-simultaneously (non-concurrently). In concurrent designs, patients are allocated randomly or non-randomly. Uncontrolled trials only have one group, which is called the interventional group. They do not have any control groups for comparison.^{3,4}

Systematic reviews comprehensively summarize the available information on specific subject while meta-analyses combine data from different published studies to estimate the overall effect size. Systematic review consists of the review of published papers. On the other hand, meta-analysis includes review and quantitative assessment.^{3,4}

Study designs vary depending on the research purpose, resources, and ethical concerns. Each of them has different disadvantages and advantages. Researchers can provide trustworthy and robust evidence to inform clinical practitioners, policymakers and enhance patients' health by using suitable study designs.

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